

Solvent extraction of copper(II) from sulfate media using neutral extractants, Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923

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Solvent extraction of copper(II) from sulfate media using neutral phosphine oxide extractants Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 in toluene has been performed. The extraction of Cu^{II} is quantitative in 0.8 and 0.1 M CH_3COONa with 0.025 M Cyanex-921 and 0.25 M Cyanex-923 in toluene, respectively. The extracted Cu^{II} from the organic phases of both the extractants is stripped out with 4.0 M CH_3COOH and determined spectrophotometrically. Effects of various parameters, such as sodium acetate concentration, reagent concentration, effect of various diluents and diverse ions on the extraction of copper are also studied. The extraction reactions proceed by solvation and their probable extracted species are $[\text{Cu}(\text{Ac})_2.2(\text{Cyanex-921})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Ac})_2.2(\text{Cyanex-921})]$.

Cyanex reagents have been employed for the extraction of Cu^{II} . Bis(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)phosphinic acid (Cyanex-272) quantitatively extracts copper(II) from NaNO_3 solution at pH 4.0¹, while partial extraction of copper(II) was observed with tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide (Cyanex-921) from 1.0 M HCl or 1.0–7.0 M $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{HClO}_4/\text{HNO}_3^2$.

In the present work extraction of Cu^{II} has been carried from sulfate media using neutral phosphine oxides extractants, Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923.

Results and Discussion

Effect of sodium acetate and reagent concentration on extraction : The effect of acetate ion concentration on the percentage extraction of copper(II) with Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 in toluene was studied in the range 0.001–2.0 M CH_3COONa . The extraction of copper(II) in the organic phases of Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 was found quantitative in the acetate range of 0.6–2.0 and 0.07–0.5 M, respectively. Hence, the extraction of copper(II) with Cyanex-921 was carried out at fixed acetate concentration of 0.8 M while that with Cyanex-923 at 0.1 M CH_3COONa .

Copper(II) was extracted with various concentration of Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 in toluene from 5×10^{-1} – 2.5×10^{-4} M with 0.8 M and 0.1 M CH_3COONa , and it was found that extraction increased with the increase in the reagent concentration. Copper(II) can be extracted quantitatively with 0.025 M Cyanex-921 and 0.25 M Cyanex-923 in toluene.

Effect of stripping agents : The metal ion Cu^{II} was

stripped out from organic phases of Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 with different strengths of acids and $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$. The complete recovery of Cu^{II} from metal loaded Cyanex-921 was found with 4.0 M CH_3COOH and 4.0 M $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solution, while from the organic phase of Cyanex-923 it was with 4.0 M CH_3COOH and 2.0 M $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$, respectively.

Effect of various diluents : The extraction of Cu^{II} with Cyanex-921 was found to be quantitative with toluene, xylene, cyclohexane, *n*-hexane and carbon tetrachloride, while with dichloromethane (95.9%), methyl isobutyl ketone (86.9%) and chloroform (65.0%) it was incomplete. On the other hand, with Cyanex-923, the extraction was quantitative with toluene, xylene, cyclohexane, *n*-hexane, carbon tetrachloride and dichloromethane, whereas with methyl isobutyl ketone (91.6%) and chloroform (71.8%) it was poor. Toluene was preferred as the best diluents for the extraction of Cu^{II} with both the extractants since it provided better phase separation.

Nature of extracted species : It was necessary to evaluate the distribution coefficient (*D*) while varying the extractant concentration to ascertain the nature of the extracted species. Therefore, the composition of the extracted species was first ascertained from the linear plots of $\log D_{\text{Cu}}$ vs $\log [\text{Cyanex-921}]$ and $\log D_{\text{Cu}}$ vs $\log [\text{Cyanex-923}]$ at fixed acetate concentration of 0.8 and 0.1 M, respectively. The slopes obtained were 1.94 and 1.96 which indicate that two ligands react with one mole of Cu^{II} ion. Hence, the probable composition of the extractable species of cop-

per(II) is 1 : 2 with both the reagents. The linear plots of $\log D_{Cu}$ vs $\log [Ac^-]$ with slopes 1.96 and 1.88 with Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923, respectively, suggest that two moles of acetate ions are used in the reaction process. Therefore, the probable extractable species formed are $[Cu(Ac)_2 \cdot 2(Cyanex-921)]$ and $[Cu(Ac)_2 \cdot 2(Cyanex-923)]$.

Effect of temperature : Extraction of copper(II) with 0.025 M Cyanex-921 and 0.25 M Cyanex-923 in toluene at a fixed acetate concentration of 0.2 and 0.01 M, respectively, was carried out at different temperatures (upto 343 K). The distribution ratio decreased with increase in temperature. The slopes obtained from the linear plots of $\log D_{Cu}$ vs $1000/T$ were 0.95 and 1.01, respectively. The ΔH values obtained are -18.19 and -19.34 kJ mol⁻¹, indicating that the reactions are exothermic in nature.

Effect of diverse ions : Copper(II) was extracted in the presence of large number of foreign ions. The tolerance limit was set such that the diverse ions caused interference of $\pm 2.0\%$ in the extraction. It was found that the alkali metals were highly tolerated while EDTA and Zn^{II} interfered strongly (Table 1).

Table 1. Tolerance limit of foreign ions on percentage extraction of 50 µg of Cu^{II}

Ions	Tolerance limit (µg)	
	Cyanex-921	Cyanex-923
K ^I , Na ^I , Li ^I , Cs ^I , Mg ^{II}	<1000	<950
Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , SO ₃ ²⁻ , I ⁻ , S ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , ClO ₄ ⁻	<800	<775
Mn ^{II} , V ^V , Cr ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Ni ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	<500	<440
Ti ^{IV} , Cd ^{II} , Rb ^I , Ag ^I	<200	<175
Ga ^{III} , Be ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Tl ^{III}	<100	<80
EDTA, Zn ^{II}	<5	<5

Separation of Cu^{II} from multicomponent mixture by Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 : Copper(II) was separated from various metals by exploring the differences in their extraction and stripping conditions. The mixture of Cu^{II}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II} and Co^{II} was resolved by equilibrating it with 0.025 M Cyanex-921 or 0.25 M Cyanex-923 in toluene from 0.8 M or 0.1 M CH₃COONa solution, respectively, when only Cu^{II} got extracted in the organic phase which was stripped with 4.0 M CH₃COOH. The pH of the aqueous phase containing Be^{II}, Zn^{II} and Co^{II} was adjusted to 8.0 and then again equilibrated with 0.005 M Cyanex-921 or 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene when Be^{II} and Zn^{II} were extracted in the organic phase while Co^{II} remained unextracted in aqueous phase. From the organic phase, Zn^{II} and Be^{II} were separated by taking advantage of difference in the stripping agents. Be^{II} was stripped first with 0.5 M NaOH and deter-

mined by quinalizarin method and then Zn^{II} stripped with 0.3 M HNO₃ and 1.0 M HCl from Cyanex-921 and Cyanex-923 extracted phases, respectively, and determined by murexide method³. Similarly, Cu^{II} from various other metal ions was separated by both the extractants and the results summarized in Tables 2 and 3. Hg^{II}, Tl^{III}, Al^{III}, Be^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Ti^{IV} were determined by reported methods⁴.

Table 2. Separation of Cu^{II} from multicomponent mixtures with Cyanex 921 in toluene

Sl. no.	Mixture	Amount taken (µg)	pH / acidity	Extractant Cyanex-921	Stripping agents	% Recovery
1.	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.025 M	4.0 M	99.2
				CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COOH	
		15	8.0	0.005 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.3
			20	8.0	0.005 M	3.0 M HNO ₃
2.	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.025 M	4.0 M	99.8
				CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COOH	
		15	8.0	0.005 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.1
			20	8.0	0.005 M	3.0 M HNO ₃
3.	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.025 M	4.0 M	99.8
				CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COOH	
		20	8.0	0.005 M	3.0 M HNO ₃	99.7
			50	8.0	0.005 M	Unextracted
4.	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.025 M	4.0 M	99.6
				CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COOH	
		15	8.0	0.005 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.2
			20	8.0	0.005 M	3.0 M HNO ₃
5.	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.025 M	4.0 M	99.5
				CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COOH	
		50	2.0	0.005 M	4.0 M HCl	99.4
			50	7.0 M HCl	0.005 M	Water
	50	7.0 M HCl	0.005 M	Unextracted	99.5	

Conclusion : The results reveal that the concentration of reagent required for the extraction of copper(II) with Cyanex-921 (0.025 M) is less compared to Cyanex-923 where it required 0.25 M. This may be due to the presence of high percentage of the active components in Cyanex-921 (99%)⁵ compared to Cyanex-923 (92.4%). Hence, Cyanex-921 is a stronger extractant for copper than Cyanex-923. Incomplete extraction was observed with Cyanex-925⁶ (<30%), di-*n*-butylthiophosphoric acid and di-*n*-butyl-dithiophosphoric acid (90%). The equilibration period (5 min) for extraction was found less with both the extractants while more in case of 1-decylimidazole (20 min)⁷, Noval

ditertiary amine (20 min)⁸ and *N*-benzoyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine (60 min)⁹.

Table 3. Separation of Cu^{II} from multicomponent mixtures with Cyanex 923 in toluene

Sl. no.	Mixture	Amount taken (µg)	pH/ acidity	Extractant Cyanex-923	Stripping agent	%Recovery
1.	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.25 M	4.0 M	99.8
			CH ₃ COONa		CH ₃ COOH	
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.6
	Zn ^{II}	20	8.0	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.2
2.	Co ^{II}	50	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.2
	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.25 M	4.0 M	99.7
			CH ₃ COONa		CH ₃ COOH	
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.6
3.	Zn ^{II}	20	8.0	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.5
	Fe ^{III}	50	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.8
	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.25 M	4.0 M	99.8
			CH ₃ COONa		CH ₃ COOH	
4.	Zn ^{II}	20	8.0	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.7
	Hg ^{II}	50	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.4
	Al ^{III}	15	5.0	0.005 M	1.0 M HCl	99.8
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.2
5.	Zn ^{II}	20	8.0	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.6
	Cu ^{II}	50	8.0	0.005 M	Unextracted	99.8
	Cu ^{II}	50	0.8 M	0.25 M	4.0 M	99.8
			CH ₃ COONa		CH ₃ COOH	
	Tl ^{III}	50	2.0	0.00125 M	3.0 M HCl	99.8
	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M HCl	0.005 M	Water	99.4
	Ti ^{IV}	50	6.0 M HCl	0.005 M	Unextracted	99.3

The method was applied for the analysis of copper in pharmaceutical samples. The results were found to be in good agreement with the theoretical values (recovery 99.2 ± 0.3 to 99.6 ± 0.2%).

Experimental

Cyanex-921 (tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide) and Cyanex-923 (Cytec Industries) were used as such. A known amount CuSO₄·5H₂O dissolved in a minimum quantity of H₂SO₄ was diluted to 1 litre with double-distilled water and standardized¹⁰. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. An Elico LI-120 pH meter with combined electrode, and a GBC 911A spectrophotometer with 10 mm cortex quartz cuvettes were used.

Procedure : An aliquot containing 50 µg of Cu^{II} in 10 ml was equilibrated separately with equal volume of Cyanex-921 or Cyanex-923 dissolved in toluene for the required shaking time (5 min) in 0.8 and 0.1 M CH₃COONa solution, respectively. The organic phase containing the metal extracted species was then stripped with CH₃COOH, CH₃COONH₄, HCl, HNO₃ and H₂SO₄. Cu^{II} was stripped

quantitatively with 4.0 M CH₃COOH and determined spectrophotometrically¹¹. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature except the effect of temperature on distribution equilibria.

Analysis of real pharmaceutical samples : The proposed methods were employed for the analysis of copper in pharmaceutical samples like Riconia (salza) (Delta Aromatic Pvt. Ltd.) and Becadexamin (Glaxo India). Riconia sample was treated with the minimum amount of concentrated sulfuric acid, the solution diluted with water, filtered to remove the residue, diluted to 250 ml and then analyzed for copper content¹². Becadexamin capsule was dissolved in aqua regia and the solution evaporated to dryness, residue dissolved in minimum amount of sulfuric acid solution and water, filtered and diluted to 100 ml. and analyzed for copper content¹².

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